

**MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF ALUMINUM MATRIX COMPOSITES REINFORCED BY
SHORT FIBERS AND PROCESSED BY COMPOCASTING**

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ABSTRACT

Composites made of chopped SiC fibers or whiskers embedded in an Al 7Si 0.6Mg foundry alloy were obtained by compocasting, with a fiber volume fraction usually ranging from 0 to 15%. Mechanical tests performed at room temperature show that the fibers increase the stiffness, hardness and dynamic toughness with respect to the unreinforced alloy. On the contrary, ductility and impact rupture energy are strongly lowered. The stiffness is maintained up to about 300-350°C. The strength of the composites is higher than that of the unreinforced alloy only at high temperatures. The poor observed failure strength is related to the distribution of the fibers in the interglobular eutectic and to the lack of preferred orientation. It is thought that it could be improved by squeeze-casting or extrusion.

INTRODUCTION

During the last decade, industry has shown a marked interest in light alloy matrix composite processing techniques such as preform infiltration by squeeze casting. However, other methods avoid the use (and therefore the preparation) of ceramic preforms and lead either to near net shape casting or transformable semi-product manufacturing. Making use of the rheocasting advantages for incorporating short ceramic fibers in a metal matrix, compocasting could be a suitable technique for low cost mass production of metal matrix composites (MMC) [1]. Nevertheless, more investigation has to

be performed in order to evaluate and to improve the mechanical performances of this type of MMC. Particularly, the processing conditions need to be better defined and adjusted to specific applications.

With this aim, aluminum alloy matrix composites (AMC) reinforced by short fibers or whiskers have been processed by compocasting. The mechanical behavior of the materials have been examined through both static and dynamic tests allowing to determine the rigidities, the yielding and ultimate tensile strengths, the rupture strain, the bending resistance as well as the dynamic rupture work and toughness. Furthermore, tensile tests performed at high temperatures and fractographic examinations complete the mechanical evaluation of the materials.

MATERIALS

The processing conditions and the morphologies of the composites have been described and detailed elsewhere [1]. Their main features can be summarized as follows:

(1) the reinforcement is constituted by either short SiC fiber (i.e. Nicalon type) about 10-15 microns in diameter, 1-3-6 mm in length, $E=190-200$ GPa, $\sigma_R= 2500$ MPa, or SiC whiskers (from Tokai) about 0.2-0.5 micron in diameter, 50-200 microns in length, $E= 700$ GPa, $\sigma_R= 3-14$ GPa,

(2) the reinforcement is incorporated under vacuum or inert gas in a semi-solid Al-7Si-0.6Mg alloy after the usual metallurgical treatment of the melt,

(3) the resulting compounds containing up to 15 vol.% of reinforcement are poured by gravity in preheated molds. Some of them are submitted to a squeeze casting procedure to increase the reinforcement volume fraction V_f up to 40% by eliminating a fraction of the liquid alloy,

(4) after gravity casting, the primary phase is globular and the smaller in size as V_f is high; the reinforcement is located in the interglobular eutectics and is homogeneously distributed in the quasi-isotropic composites whatever the type of reinforcement (Figure 1). The use of an additional squeeze casting operation leads to eliminate the eutectics and gives rise to a preferential orientation of the fibers perpendicular to the pressing axis,

(5) the occurrence of pores is exceptional (it is easily detected during mechanical testing and evidenced by fractographic examination),

(6) before machining and mechanical testing, the materials are submitted to a metallurgical treatment T6 (540°C during 4 hours; water quenching; 180°C during 4 hours).

Figure 1. Optical micrograph of AMC composite processed by compocasting.

Figure 2. Tensile tests curves of Al 7Si 0.6Mg alloy and composites
solid line: stress-strain curves
dashed line: cumulative acoustic emission-strain curves.

Figure 3. Determination of the elastic modulus by bending tests with various spans, with the following formula: $1/E_q = 1/E + A \cdot h^2 / G \cdot L^2$
solid line: $A = 1.2$
dashed line: $A = 1.5$

STATIC TESTING AT ROOM TEMPERATURE

The materials exhibit an elasto-plastic behavior as illustrated in Figure 2 allowing to derive the usual mechanical characteristics.

Stiffness

The material stiffness has been determined from the own frequencies of vibration of parallelepipedic specimens ($10 \times 10 \times 100 \text{ mm}^3$), as well as by bending tests (specimen size: $10 \times 10 \times 100 \text{ mm}^3$) and under tensile loading (specimen size: $4 \times 8 \times 60 \text{ mm}^3$).

The own frequencies (measured with a Grindo Sonic apparatus) lead to the Young's modulus E and shear modulus G reported in Table 1. These values are in good agreement with those derived from both bending and tensile tests performed as follows:

(1) in bending tests, the use of various spans to measure the deflexion of the specimens enables to assess E and G from the change in the bulk stiffness of the materials as illustrated in Figure 3,

(2) in tensile tests, the strains imposed to the specimens at a rate of about $40 \times 10^{-6} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ are measured with an extensometer and strain gages, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Although the increases in stiffness due to the incorporation of the fibers are rather small, as illustrated in Table 1 and Figure 4, the experimental data are in good agreement with numerical values derived from a finite elements computation [2]. As expected, increasing V_f slightly lowers Poisson's ratios but no modification of the rigidities can be related to change in the fiber length from 1 to 6 mm. This feature leads to consider the fiber-matrix bonding as good to enable the load transfer.

On the other hand, no evident rigidification corresponds to the incorporation of 8 vol.% SiC whiskers. The reinforcement size and content are so small that the whiskers located in the eutectics do not achieve any bridging between the globular grains of the primary phase.

Strength

Yielding and ultimate strengths σ_E and σ_R as well as rupture strain ϵ_R have been derived from the tensile and bending tests and are listed in Table 2. The acoustic

emission during the tensile tests is used to define the position of the yielding on the stress-strain curves. It clearly appears that:

(1) for the range of fiber length and volume fraction which have been studied, the yielding strength is not increased with respect to the unreinforced matrix,

Figure 4. Elastic modulus versus volume fraction of SiC fibers solid line: calculated values by finite element analysis; plotted points: experimental data.

Figure 5. Evolution of the hardness of AMC processed by compocasting.

Figure 6. SEM micrographs of Al 7Si 0.6Mg / SiC fibers composites
 (a) Vf = 8% L = 1 mm
 (b) Vf = 15% L = 1 mm.

(2) furthermore, raising the reinforcement volume fraction leads to a lowering of the rupture strength at room temperature,

(3) in fact, the performances of the composites seem to be controlled by ductility. Unfortunately, the material rupture strain is strongly decreased by the presence of the brittle ceramic. Thus, the incorporation of fibers or whiskers doesn't lead, in the present case, to a reinforcing effect of the matrix but rather to an embrittlement.

Hardness

The hardness of the composites has been assessed through Brinell indentation tests. The use of a large diameter ball (10 mm in diameter) with a load of 10 kN permits an easier evaluation of the composite resistance to brinelling effect despite the local heterogeneity of the materials. As shown in Figure 5, there is a significant improvement of the composite hardness as V_f is increased. This favorable effect is the more evidenced as the composites are not T6 heat treated and seem to be independent of the fiber type (SiC fibers or SiC whiskers).

Fractographic analysis

In order to check the validity of tests, each rupture surface was observed by SEM to point out eventual defects as illustrated in Figure 6, examination of the fractographies leads to the following remarks:

(1) the rupture surface of the light alloy matrix is slightly dimples like which indicates the occurrence of a plastic deformation despite the embrittlement effect of the fibers,

(2) however, other morphological features of the rupture surface could be related to interglobular failure,

(3) no fiber pull out phenomenon is observed,

(4) numerous fibers are fractured longitudinally .

It comes out from the previous remarks that the fiber-matrix bonding is very strong allowing an efficient load transfer. Therefore fibers should behave as an efficient reinforcement vis a vis rupture which is not the case . This failure mechanism could be related to the position of the fibers acting as crack initiators in a prestressed eutectics.

IMPACT TESTING

Impact behavior of the AMC was evaluated through instrumented Charpy impact tests. The load-time curves are shown in Figure 7. They were used to

Figure 7. Load -time curves of impact-tests

Figure 8. Temperature dependence of Young's modulus for various composites and alloy.

Figure 9. Temperature dependence of ultimate tensile strength for various composites and alloy.

determine the impact rupture energy and to derive the dynamic toughness K_{ID} from a method which has been presented elsewhere [3].

The evolution with V_f of the main features depicting the load-time curves shows that raising the fibers volume fraction can result in opposite effects .

The experimental data reported in Table 3 lead to summarize the impact behavior of the AMC as follows:

(1) the incorporation of fibers within the basic alloy leads to a simultaneous increase in dynamic toughness and decrease in impact rupture energy,

(2) the toughness increase is the more significant as the SiC fibers (Nicalon type) are long,

(3) the evolution of the toughness is not monotonous, a maximum being observed for $V_f = 8 \text{ vol.}\%$,

(4) the improvement in dynamic toughness is more effective in the case of SiC whiskers than for 1 mm length SiC Nicalon fibers.

HIGH TEMPERATURE BEHAVIOR IN TENSION

High temperature tensile tests were performed up to about 400°C with a strain rate of $170 \times 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$ on cylindrical specimens (7 mm in diameter, 60 mm in length). After heating at a speed of $3\text{-}4^\circ\text{C mn}^{-1}$, the specimens were maintained during 15 mn at the testing temperature before loading. Deformations were measured with a water cooled extensometer. The results are reported in Figures 8 to 10 and suggest the following comments:

(1) the reinforcing effect of the fibers with respect to stiffness is effective up to 300°C ($V_f = 8\%$) or 350°C ($V_f = 15\%$). Above these temperatures similar low values of Young's modulus are observed for both the composites and basic alloy,

(2) the rupture strength of the aluminum alloy is not improved by the fibers below 300°C. Above this temperature , the strength is increased of about 50% ($\sigma_R = 75 \text{ MPa}$ at 325°C for $V_f = 15\%$),

(3) the rupture strain ϵ_R of SiC Nicalon reinforced AMC is kept very low up to 250°C (0.4-0.5%), whereas in the case of SiC whiskers, ϵ_R increases as soon as the temperature raises. At high temperatures, the AMC curves tend to reach that of the basic alloy,

(4) the fractographic examination of the rupture surfaces confirms the strong increase in ductility at high temperatures (i.e. dimples like network is more easily evidenced).

(5) apparently, the fiber length is not a significant parameter for the high temperature performances of the AMC obtained by compocasting.

TABLE 1
Elastic characteristics of AMC
processed by compositing

Material	V _f	Grindo Sonic			Tensile Tests			Bending Tests		
		E GPa	G GPa	ν calc.	E GPa	ν calc.	G GPa	E GPa	G GPa	ν calc.
AS7G06 T0 treatment	0	73	27	0,352	73	0,35	27,03	74	27,25	0,35
AS7G06 SiC Nicalon fibers Compositing 600°C T0 Treatment	8	79	29,5	0,339	79	0,34	29,48	80,15	29,95	0,338
	15	85	32	0,328	85	0,33	31,96	86,16	32,96	
AS7G06 SiC Tokamax whiskers Compositing 600°C T0 Treatment	8	73	28	0,304	73	0,30	28	74	28,25	0,31
AS7G06 SiC Nicalon fibers Squeeze-casting 660°C 40 MPa T0 Treatment	40	100	40	0,25	-	-	-	-	-	-

TABLE 2
Strengths and rupture strains
of AMC processed by compositing

Materials	V _f	Tensile Tests			Bending Tests		
		Y.S. MPa	U.T.S. MPa	ε _R %	Y.S. MPa	U.T.S. MPa	S ₀ mm
AS7G06 T0 Treatment	0	130 ± 5	330 ± 10	1.9 ± 0.1	180 ± 5	no rupture	no rupture
AS7G06 SiC Nicalon fibers Compositing 600°C T0 Treatment	8	130 ± 5	285 ± 10	0.5 ± 0.1	180 ± 5	375 ± 10	5 ± 0.1
	15	130 ± 5	210 ± 10	0.4 ± 0.1	180 ± 5	280 ± 10	3.35 ± 0.1
AS7G06 SiC Tokamax whiskers Compositing 600°C T0 Treatment	8	120 ± 5	240 ± 10	0.6 ± 0.1	160 ± 5	280 ± 10	4.50 ± 0.1

Figure 10. Temperature dependence
of rupture strain for various
composites and alloy.

Material	K _{1ST} maxima of the force time curves MPa . m ^{1/2}	K _{1DM} dynamic toughness MPa . m ^{1/2}	Energy of Rupture KJ/m ²
AS7G06	18.50	17.40	12.82
AS7G06 8% SiC Nicalon 1mm	20.26	19.09	6.86
AS7G06 8% SiC Tokamax	20.96	20.47	7.35
AS7G06 8% SiC Nicalon 6mm	23.01	22.90	9.32
AS7G06 15% SiC Nicalon 6mm	18.43	16.30	5.58

TABLE 3
Toughness and energy of rupture
of AMC processed by compositing

CONCLUSIONS

Although,compocasting technique can be used to obtain AMC reinforced by short fibers, the resulting materials exhibit a reinforcing effect only for stiffness, hardness and dynamic toughness. The ductility as well as the impact rupture energy are strongly decreased, and the rupture strength is improved only at high temperatures. The poor performances of this type of composites vis a vis rupture could be related to the distribution pattern of the fibers which are mainly located in the interglobular eutectics without any prefered orientation.

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